

HIGH PERFORMANCE COMPOSITES BASED ON NANOPAPERS

Andreas Mautner^{1,2}, Jessica Lucenius³, Monika Österberg³ and Alexander Bismarck^{1,2}

¹Polymer and Composite Engineering group, Institute for Materials Chemistry & Research,
University of Vienna, Währinger Straße 42, 1090 Wien, Austria
Email: andreas.mautner@univie.ac.at, web page: <http://mc.univie.ac.at>

²Polymer and Composite Engineering group, Imperial College London,
South Kensington Campus, London SW7 2AZ, United Kingdom
Email: alexander.bismarck@univie.ac.at, web page: <http://www.imperial.ac.uk/pace>

³School of Chemical Technology, Department of Forest Products Technology,
Aalto University, Vuorimiehentie 1, Espoo, P.O. Box 16300, FI-00076 Aalto, Finland
Email: jessica.lucenius@aalto.fi, monika.osterberg@aalto.fi, web page: <http://www.aalto.fi>

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ABSTRACT

Nanocellulose, cellulose in the form of nanofibrils (CNF), has gained considerable attention in recent years as reinforcement agent for the production of composite materials due to its excellent mechanical and chemical properties, with the Young's modulus even outperforming glass fibers. However, so far the full potential of mechanical properties of CNF could not be exploited for the production of composites exhibiting properties comparable to state-of-the-art engineering polymer-composites with glass or carbon fibers. This is particularly true if the goal is to produce composites completely from renewable resources [1, 2]. Thus we propose a new approach to produce nanocomposites based on nanocellulose that should enable better utilization of the outstanding mechanical properties of CNF.

A new type of nanopaper from CNF has been developed and used for the production of nanocomposites. These nanopapers have been proven to exhibit significantly enhanced strength and toughness as compared to pure nanocellulose nanopapers. That is based on the introduction of various natural polysaccharides into the network of cellulose nanofibrils hindering crack propagation, thus enhancing the toughness of the material [3]. For the production of composites, these two-phase nanopapers were laminated with a standard epoxy resin. Two layers of nanopapers were laminated and these pre-forms then cured in a hot-press to result in the final composite. Of these composites, specimens for mechanical and thermo-physical measurements were produced and tested. Results indicated a significant impact of the new type of nanopapers on the mechanical properties of the composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites made from natural resources have gained significant attention during the last decade due to environmental issues associated with conventional composites produced from synthetic materials [1]. Even though progress was made in the recycling of composites, these classes of materials still substantiate a major waste problem [2]. Furthermore the requirement of fossil resources and huge amounts of chemicals and energy are drawbacks of nowadays high performance composite materials. To circumvent these drawbacks, composites based on renewable resources, utilizing clean and cheap production routes have been proposed; e.g. natural fibers based on cellulose from various sources have been employed [4]. Cellulose, as first established in 1839 by Payen [5, 6], is a natural polymer formed of poly- β (1,4)-D-glucan macromolecules and one of the most abundant organic polymers on earth [7, 8]. Even though utilizing these renewable base materials resulted in proper composites with acceptable mechanical properties, the performance of state-of-the-art synthetic

polymer materials or even glass or carbon fiber composites could not be matched. This is due to inherent properties of natural fibers, such as hydrophilicity and variations in quality and dimensions caused by varying weather conditions [9]. Several different approaches have been tried to deal with these issues, e.g. modification of fibrils, but still the level of high performance synthetic composites was not reached [10]. In recent years, nanofibrillated cellulose (CNF), cellulose fibrils with diameters at the nanoscale, received great attention due to their outstanding mechanical and chemical properties [7, 11] especially when utilized for the production of membranes [12, 13] or composites [4, 14-23]. Till date several approaches to utilize CNF in composites have been proposed and tried.

One approach to utilize the potential of CNF is to directly reinforce a soft matrix with a small amount of CNF resulting in improved mechanical strength provided there is an affinity between the matrix and the cellulose fibrils. Exemplarily, Mikkonen [24] used 5 to 15 wt.-% CNF to reinforce films of spruce O-acetyl galactoglucomannan while Peng [25] and Hansen [26] utilized CNF to reinforce xylan films. Additionally, CNF has been used to reinforce thermoplastic starch and chitosan-based composites [27]; an addition of 10 to 20 % CNF improved the composites' thermal stability and mechanical properties, i.e. the tensile strength and Young's modulus were significantly increased on the expense of the elongation at break. Another promising approach was the manufacture of hierarchical composites made from cellulose micro-fibers derived from natural resources, too, together with CNF [15]. Additionally, the use of CNF as sole reinforcing agent was also regarded as possible track en route to high performance composites [23]. It was shown that key to utilizing most of the fibers' mechanical properties is to introduce as highest fiber loadings as possible [9]. Thus using CNF-nanopapers as scaffold for the production of composites seems appropriate. Unfortunately, pure CNF films are relatively brittle thus requiring modifications in order to gain enduring films. Recently, Sehaqui et al. [28] showed increased hydrophobicity and wet-strength through esterification of pre-formed nanopapers. Apparently, modification performed in wet-state led to decreased dry-strength of the nanopaper, while solely surface treatment usually retains the dry strength of the CNF film [29]. Mimicking the structure of strong natural materials, such as wood is another approach. This can be achieved by mixing CNF with a small amount of a soft polymer, whereby the CNF network provides strength and stiffness while the role of the soft polymer is to hinder crack propagation, thus enhancing the toughness of the material. This approach ultimately aims at mechanical properties that exceed the individual properties of both materials, which usually is not possible in conventional composite manufacturing. Exemplarily, CNF containing a high amount of anionic charges were combined with a cationic blockcopolymer and synergistic effects have been observed [30, 31]. Unfortunately, ionic interactions between anionic fibrils and cationic polymer chains removed water from the CNF gel, whereby systems relying on ionic interactions could be susceptible to aggregation. This demonstrates the importance to control the state of dispersion and aggregation of CNF by controlling the interactions between the fibrils in order to achieve high strength and stiffness in cellulose nanopapers [32]. In natural composite materials such as wood, silk, mollusk shells or bone, non-ionic interactions are present, mainly van der Waals interactions and multiple hydrogen bonds. Accordingly, biomimetic composites from CNF and poly(ethylene glycol) grafted carboxymethyl cellulose [33] were studied in which interactions between the polymer and CNF are non-ionic. It was found that in this system, the water swollen polysaccharide was able to lubricate the interface between fibrils during film formation. Consequently, an even and strong film was formed.

We here present strong and tough CNF films (also called nanopapers) that were developed by introducing polysaccharides such as oxidized, hydrolyzed guar gum galactomannan or galactoglucomannan into the matrix of a CNF film. Thermal (thermogravimetric analysis, TGA) and mechanical (tensile tests) properties of these films were analyzed. Furthermore, in order to utilize their very good mechanical performance, these two-phase CNF films were manufactured into high loading CNF-polymer composites by a lamination process. The manufacture of these types of nanopapers along their thermal (TGA) and mechanical (dynamic mechanical analysis, DMTA) characterization and the production and testing of composites made from these nanopapers is studied.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Cellulose nanofibrils (CNF) were prepared by disintegration of unmodified never dried industrial bleached birch pulp. The pulp was passed six times through a high-pressure fluidizer (Microfluidics, M-110Y, Microfluidics Int. Co., Newton, USA) according to a procedure described previously [29].

Two types of water-soluble polysaccharides (WSPS) were used for introduction into the CNF network. Commercial guar gum galactomannan (GG, $M_w > 1000$ kDa) from Sigma Aldrich (Lot#041M 0058V, Pcode 10011170894) was used after enzymatic modification. Spruce galactoglucomannan (GGM, *Picea abies*, M_w 20 to 60 kDa) was obtained from the process water of a Finnish pulp mill in an industrial-scale isolation trial after ethanol precipitation [34].

Enzymes were used for hydrolyzing and oxidizing GG. Endo-1,4- β -mannanase (Lot 00803, from *Aspergillus niger*, EC number 3.2.1.78, 42 U mg^{-1}) was received from Megazyme (Wicklow, Ireland), galactose oxidase (GO, G7400, 3685 U g^{-1} , EC 1.1.3.9), catalase (from bovine liver, C30, 22000 U mg^{-1}) and horseradish peroxidase (HRP, P8250, type II, 181 U mg^{-1}) were received from Sigma-Aldrich.

Epoxy resin Araldite LY 556 and amine hardener XB 3473 were purchased from Mouldlife (Suffolk, UK). The water used in the experiments was deionized and further purified with a UV unit (Synergy Millipore, Molsheim, France).

2.2 Methods

2.2.1. Hydrolysis of GG with mannanase

GG was partially hydrolyzed using endo-1,4- β -mannanase. GG was dissolved in deionized water to obtain a 1.0 % (w/v) solution, the enzyme added and the solution incubated at 40 °C in a water bath for 4 h. In order to inactivate the enzyme it was heated to 100 °C for 10 min. The samples were centrifuged at 5000 rpm and the supernatant was collected and freeze-dried.

2.2.2. Oxidation of GG with galactose oxidase

Partially hydrolyzed GG was enzymatically oxidized (OGG) whereby the dosage of the enzymes was based on the amount of galactose present in the GG sample: 1.50 U of GO, 150 U of catalase and 0.9 U of HRP per mg of galactose. The 1 % (w/v) solutions of GG were stirred in the presence of the enzymes at 4 °C. The oxidation time used was 72 h, afterwards the sample was heated to 90 °C during mixing in order to inactivate the enzymes.

2.2.3. Determination of the molecular weight

Size exclusion chromatography (SEC) was used to determine the M_w of GG hydrolyzed with mannanase. M_w values were calculated using a dn/dc value of 0.15 $mL g^{-1}$. The hydrolyzed GG was dissolved in 0.1 M $NaNO_3$ by stirring for 7 days and filtered with a 0.45 μm filter according to the procedure in [35].

2.2.4. Determination of the degree of oxidation

Gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MS) was used to determine the degree of oxidation (DO), as described in [35]. Briefly, the samples (1 mg of polysaccharide) were deuterium labelled with $NaBD_4$, precipitated and acid methanolized. The galactosyl units of GG were selectively oxidized with GO. The degree of oxidation was calculated by comparison of the ratio of m/z 361 and m/z 362 ions of silylated galactosyls, where 361 corresponded to the unoxidized galactosyls and 362 to the oxidized galactosyls containing the deuterium label [35].

2.2.5. Film preparation

To avoid aggregation of the nanofibrils, the CNF suspension was diluted to 0.8 wt.-% (105 ml, corresponding to a dry mass of 0.84 g) and mixed overnight with a magnetic stirrer. To this suspension, 2 wt.-% (based on CNF dry content) of water soluble polysaccharides OGG or GGM, respectively, were added and further stirred for 24 h to ensure good homogeneity [3]. Sequential filtering and pressing [29] was used to prepare the CNF-WSPS films. The final film thickness was $55 \pm 5 \mu\text{m}$.

2.2.6. Composite preparation

Composites were manufactured by laminating pure or modified CNF films with a two-component epoxy resin. Commercially available epoxy resin Araldite LY 556 plus 23 phr amine hardener XB 3473 were mixed and degassed under vacuum at 80 °C for 10 min. Two CNF films (diameter 120 mm) were laminated on a K Printing Proofer (RK PrintCoat Instruments Ltd, Hertfordshire, UK) at room temperature by adjusting a layer thickness of 50 μm for the epoxy resin. After lamination the CNF film-epoxy laminate was sandwiched between two Teflon-films in a custom-made mold and put into a hot-press. The hot-press was heated to 120 °C and upon reaching this temperature the sandwich was pressed at 2 t for 2 h. Afterwards the temperature was raised to 180 °C for an additional 2 h. The composite was de-molded after cooling down under pressure to room temperature. From the final composites, specimens for mechanical testing were prepared by cutting the shape of rectangular sheets sized 40 x 5 mm².

2.2.7. Thermogravimetric Analysis

The thermal degradation behavior of nanocomposites in nitrogen and air, respectively, was investigated using high resolution modulated TGA (Discovery TGA, TA Instruments, Eschborn, Germany). A sample size of approximately 5 mg was used. The samples were heated from 30 to 650 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ and a gas flow rate of 25 mL min⁻¹. The onset of degradation was computed to be the temperature at which the mass loss rate was exceeding 0.2 % per °C.

2.2.8. Mechanical properties

Tensile mechanical properties of the CNF(-WSPS) films were measured using a MTS 400/M vertical tester (MTS System Corporation, Eden Prairie, USA), with a 200 N load cell (Adamel Lhomargy serial num. 115341, MTS). The adjustable speed accuracy was 0.1 % and the resolution for the crosshead displacement 0.01 mm. Strips with dimensions of 50 × 15 mm² were cut from the uniform CNF(-WSPS) film with a lab paper cutter. The thickness was separately measured for each specimen before measurements at three different spots with a Lorentzen & Wettre paper thickness meter. The average thickness of these three different measurements was used to normalize the measured force when calculating the tensile stress. The grip distance was 40 mm and the testing velocity 0.5 mm min⁻¹. The samples were conditioned for at least 3 days at 23 °C and 50 % RH before testing. At least 5 parallel samples were tested.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of the composites was performed with a G2 RSA (TA Instruments, Eschborn, Germany) in three point bending mode. Specimens sized 40 x 5 mm² were cut from the composites and tested between -100 and 200 °C at 3 °C min⁻¹ and a frequency of 1 Hz with a strain of 0.05 % and a span distance of 25 mm.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Structure, molecular weight and degree of oxidation of the polysaccharides

The polysaccharides studied were the mannans GG and GGM, which contain ca. 40 % and 10 % terminal α -D-galactosyl residues, respectively, directly attached to C-6 of the mannosyl units of the backbone [36]. GG with a reduced molecular weight was prepared by partial hydrolysis with β -mannanase. According to size exclusion chromatography, the Mw of the hydrolyzed GG was approximately 30 kDa and the hydrodynamic radius of the sample was 4.7 nm.

Figure 1: Structures and modification of polysaccharides.

The DO of oxidized galactosyls in the OGG samples were 67 % and 80 %, respectively. The total relative amount of oxidized galactosyls in the final modified CNF film was respectively 0.45 % and 0.60 % of total carbohydrates. Due to the selective oxidation of the galactosyls of GG, the backbone chain remains unmodified facilitating good compatibility with cellulose and the viscosity of the OGG solutions was low at all degrees of oxidation and therefore mixing of the solutions with CNF suspension was easy.

3.2 Mechanical and thermal behavior of the modified CNF films

The introduction of polysaccharides into the matrix of CNF films accounts for a change in both thermal and mechanical properties of these films.

3.2.1 Thermal behavior of the CNF films

The thermal degradation behavior of CNF films was tested in both nitrogen and air atmosphere. Under inert atmosphere (Figure 2), a two-step degradation regime was found for all types of films. During the initial phase between 30 and 150 °C, no significant difference was found for the different CNF films: around 5 % of moisture was removed and the onset of the first thermal degradation step, attributed to cleavage of glycosidic linkages of cellulose [37], took place at around 270 °C. However, the final degradation, attributed to the degradation of the six-member cyclic structure of cellulose (pyran) [4], took place at increased temperatures for the two-phase films starting at around 500 °C, whereas the pure CNF film started to completely degrade already at 470 °C. This behavior could possibly be explained by an increased network density in which the WSPS occupy otherwise empty space within the CNF network.

Figure 2: TGA of (modified) CNF films under nitrogen (left) and air (right).

In air atmosphere, again around 5 % of moisture was removed between 30 and 150 °C and the onset of the first degradation step, attributed to the degradation of low-molecular weight compounds took place at 250 °C for all kinds of CNF films tested [38, 39]. The onset of the second degradation step, attributed to the degradation of pyran structures, was for all types of CNF films around 430 °C whereby only minor deviations occurred depending on the polysaccharide component used.

3.2.2 Mechanical behavior of the CNF films

The addition of soft polymers has already been demonstrated to lubricate CNF films to improve the mechanical properties of these films [29, 33]. In particular the tensile strength can be increased significantly. This behavior was also found to be present for the materials in this study [3]. The tensile strength of unmodified CNF films could be improved by more than 50 % through addition of OGG (DO of 67 %) or GGM, (Figure 3). However, this takes place on the expense of stiffness. The modulus slightly decreased for OGG from 9 GPa for unmodified CNF to 7.9 GPa. For GGM (8.7 GPa), also a minor decrease could be found. However, this decrease was not statistically significant.

Figure 3: Modulus and tensile strength of (modified) CNF films from tensile tests.[3]

These results were as to be expected for two-phase films, in which highly crystalline CNF form the stiff part and the water-soluble polysaccharides act as plasticizer, enhancing the ductility of the composite. Previous studies utilizing a quartz crystal microbalance showed that these polymers form a water-swollen dissipative layer on the CNF surface [40]. Thus it can be assumed that the

polysaccharides enhance the dispersibility of CNF during film formation, which is crucial to avoid aggregates and defects in the final film.

3.3 Epoxy-CNF composites

Composites were produced from a two-component epoxy resin and unmodified CNF films, as well as CNF films modified with OGG (DO of 80 %) or GGM, respectively, via a laminating technique. Resulting composite films exhibited thicknesses around 100 μm and a volume fibril content of around 90 %.

3.3.1 Thermal behavior of the composites

The thermal degradation behavior of the composites was tested in both nitrogen and air atmosphere. Under inert atmosphere (Figure 4), a two-step degradation regime was found for all three types of composites, similar to those of the pure films, demonstrating that the overall thermal behavior was governed by the films which make up more than 90 % (w/v) of the composite. Opposed to the pure CNF films, during the initial phase between 30 and 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, only around 3 % (compared to 5 % for the CNF films) of moisture was removed, which was attributed to increased overall hydrophobicity introduced by the epoxy resin. However, just as for the CNF films, the onset of the first thermal degradation step, attributed to cleavage of glycosidic linkages of cellulose [37], took place at around 270 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The final degradation step, attributed to the degradation of the six-member cyclic structure of cellulose (pyran), was different for the different sets of polysaccharide phases within the CNF films. Pure CNF film composites and those with GGM underwent the second degradation step around 510 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively, whereas for OGG around 470 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ final degradation set on. The reason for this might be connected to the presence of oxidation-products in OGG, which catalyze the degradation of the matrix.

Figure 4: TGA of CNF-epoxy composites under nitrogen (left) and air (right).

In air atmosphere, again a smaller amount of moisture was removed between 30 and 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared to the CNF-WSPS films (3 % opposed to 5 %). Additionally, the onset of the first degradation step, attributed to the degradation of low-molecular weight compounds [38, 39], took place at 270 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (compared to 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for CNF films), demonstrating the influence of the protecting matrix of the epoxy resin. Also for the onset of the second degradation step, attributed to the degradation of pyran structures, only slight deviations occurred again depending on the polysaccharide component used around 430 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ similar to those of the CNF-WSPS films.

3.3.2 Mechanical behavior of the CNF-epoxy composites

The mechanical performance of CNF-epoxy composites was tested by means of DMTA in three point bending mode. The storage modulus at 20 °C was used to compare the different types of composites (Figure 5).

Figure 5: DMTA: Storage modulus of CNF-epoxy composites at 20 °C.

As for the (modified) CNF films, the modulus was dependent on the type of polysaccharide that was introduced into the matrix of the CNF film. Whereas for composites made from pure CNF films a storage modulus of 20 GPa was established, this value was slightly lower for the two-phase CNF films. GGM introduced into the matrix of CNF films lowered the storage modulus to 17.4 GPa, whereas for OGG it resulted in 17.2 GPa. This result demonstrates the influence of the WSPS as lubricant in the matrix of otherwise brittle CNF films, also when they act as reinforcement material in composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Strong two-component films were prepared by introduction of water soluble polysaccharides into a matrix of CNF films. These films were tested for their thermal and mechanical properties and subsequently processed into composites by lamination with an epoxy resin. Modified CNF films exhibit higher tensile strength compared to the unmodified CNF films on the expense of modulus, which is slightly reduced. Only a minor influence of the WSPS can be determined in terms of thermal degradation behavior, merely at the very final stage of degradation. These (modified) CNF films could be successfully turned into composites by lamination with an epoxy resin and subsequent hot-pressing. The thermal stability of these composites was mainly governed by the thermal behavior of the CNF films for they made up around 90 % (v/v) of the composites. Again, only at the very end of thermal degradation a minor influence of the different types of polysaccharide modification could be established. The mechanical properties of the composites mirrored the ones of the CNF films. From DMTA the storage modulus could be established in three point bending mode to 20 GPa for unmodified CNF-epoxy composites. As expected and intended, addition of OGG or GGM led to a little decrease of the modulus by 10 to 15 %. This was explained by the lubricating effect of the WSPS that should ultimately hinder or even stop crack propagation. Eventually, tensile properties of the composites will be established, too, to prove the strengthening effect of the polysaccharides added.

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